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PROSPLIGN

Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules

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3	Fundación Medina	MEDINA	Spain	Yes	RPO
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5	University College Dublin	UCD	Ireland	Yes	UNI
6	MAGFI ltd	MAGFI	Malta	Yes	SME
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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
WP	Work Package
SEN	Sensitive (referring to confidential project deliverables)
GPC	Gel Permeation Chromatography (used for molecular weight analysis)
HPLC	High pressure liquid chromatography
LC-MS	Liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectroscopy
FTIR	Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance

1 Executive Summary

The **PROSPLIGN** project seeks to unlock the untapped potential of lignin, a complex and chemically diverse aromatic natural polymer isolated from lignocellulosic biomass. Traditionally treated as a low-value byproduct from industries such as pulp and paper, lignin is now being re-evaluated in PROSPLIGN as a novel resource for the discovery of bioactive molecules with applications in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances. Unlike conventional approaches that aim to simplify lignin into a narrow set of aromatic chemicals for bulk applications, PROSPLIGN embraces its natural complexity, leveraging innovative chemical and enzymatic methods combined with high-throughput bioactivity screening to identify novel bioactive molecules from lignin.

This public report provides an overview of the methodology used by BFH and UCD in the PROSPLIGN project arising from Task 4.4 **to purify depolymerized mixtures of lignin to finally isolate bioactive lignin fragment**. Key aspects include:

- **Diverse chromatography methods:** the method presented here describe chromatographic methods that allows us to start with complex depolymerized mixtures and narrow down progressively the complexity until single bioactive compounds can be isolated
- **Structural characterization of isolated bioactive compounds:** mass spectroscopy techniques (e.g. LC-ESI-MS, MALDI-ToF or MS/MS) have the potentiality to identify or confirm the structure of bioactive compounds.
- **Key Findings:**
 - Mixture's complexity varies strongly within the different depolymerized lignin mixtures
 - Characterization and Fractionation of complex mixtures by HPLC-UV and flash chromatography
- **Risk Mitigation:** Challenges during fractionation and purification were addressed by developing different methods based on the complexity of the depolymerized mixtures (i.e single or multiple columns in series, different solvent mixtures, linear gradients and stepped gradients)

By establishing a robust method for fractionation and purification of depolymerized lignin mixtures, PROSPLIGN lays the groundwork for discovering high-value bioactive compounds from a natural renewal resource, contributing to the transition toward a circular bioeconomy and creating new market opportunities for lignin valorisation. The next deliverable of this task (D4.9 Preliminary report on isolation and purification of bioactive compounds) is scheduled for M20.

2 Introduction

2.1 Overview of the PROSPLIGN Project

PROSPLIGN aims to bioprospect within lignocellulosic biomass, the most abundantly available terrestrial natural resource, specifically focusing on its largely underutilised lignin fraction. Lignin is a structurally complex and chemically diverse natural polymer, with its composition varying significantly depending on both the plant source and the extraction method used to obtain it. It is important to highlight that lignin is not a single substance, but rather **lignin is a vast family of chemically diverse natural polymers**. Lignin's complexity is often seen as a challenge as conventional lignin valorisation approaches aim to "simplify" lignin into a few well-defined fractions for bulk industrial applications. In contrast, PROSPLIGN embraces lignin's complexity as an opportunity to prospect a largely untapped resource for novel bioactive molecules with potential applications in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances.

Traditionally, lignin has been considered a byproduct of industries like pulp and paper, where it is often burned for energy – however, more recently lignin has been highlighted as a natural source of aromatic chemicals and recognised as a feedstock for the production of renewable chemicals or fuels.¹ While lignin has been used as a resource for developing biobased platform chemicals to be used in the synthesis of bioactive molecules,² PROSPLIGN leverages lignin's chemical diversity for a previously unmet application: **bioprospecting—the search for new bioactive compounds**. To unlock lignin's bioactivity potential, PROSPLIGN is developing an innovative approach that combines cutting-edge chemical and enzymatic methods with advanced statistical analysis and high-throughput detection techniques. This integrated strategy aims to unlock the bioactivity potential of lignin and lay the foundation for new valorisation opportunities for lignocellulosic biomass. By developing sustainable and efficient ways to unlock lignin's potential, PROSPLIGN contributes to the broader shift towards a bio-based circular economy.

¹ Brienza, F.; Cannella, D.; Montesdeoca, D.; Cybulska, I.; Debecker, D. P. A Guide to Lignin Valorization in Biorefineries: Traditional, Recent, and Forthcoming Approaches to Convert Raw Lignocellulose into Valuable Materials and Chemicals. *RSC Sustainability* **2024**, *2* (1), 37–90. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3SU00140G>.

² (a) Lan, W.; Luterbacher, J. S. A Road to Profitability from Lignin via the Production of Bioactive Molecules. *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2019**, *5* (10), 1642–1644. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscentsci.9b00954>. (b) Afanasenko, A. M.; Wu, X.; De Santi, A.; Elgaher, W. A. M.; Kany, A. M.; Shafiei, R.; Schulze, M.; Schulz, T. F.; Hauptenthal, J.; Hirsch, A. K. H.; Barta, K. Clean Synthetic Strategies to Biologically Active Molecules from Lignin: A Green Path to Drug Discovery**. *Angewandte Chemie* **2024**, *136* (4), e202308131. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.202308131>. (c) Park, J.; Kelly, M. A.; Kang, J. X.; Seemakurti, S. S.; Ramirez, J. L.; Hatzell, M. C.; Sievers, C.; Bommarius, A. S. Production of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs) from Lignin-Derived Phenol and Catechol. *Green Chem.* **2021**, *23* (19), 7488–7498. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1GC02158C>.

A key challenge in this project is the separation of the bioactive compounds that are formed during depolymerization from the rest of the mixtures. This step is even more challenging as the molecules of interest could be formed in small yield or hide within a complex mixture. PROSPLIGN addresses this by developing a purification methodology based on chromatographic methods in combination with bioassays that enables the progressive removal of inactive molecules, ultimately allowing us to isolate the bioactive molecules of interest and unveil his chemical structure.

2.2 Objectives of this report on fractionation and purification of depolymerized mixtures

This summary report – available to the public – provides an overview of PROSPLIGN’s approach for **the fractionation and purification of depolymerized mixtures** performed by the BFH, summarising the methodology used to produce fractions from bioactive depolymerized mixtures using an automated flash column chromatography device. The fractions produced are further tested for bioactivity by Fundación Medina and Nova University of Lisbon. Lately, the fractions containing the bioactive compound are purified to isolate single molecules by preparative HPLC. Finally, the bioactive compounds isolated are characterized by means of Liquid chromatography-mass spectroscopy (LC-MS) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy by University College Dublin (UCD).

More details on the fractionation and purification process of bioactive depolymerized mixtures (particularly commercially sensitive aspects related to PROSPLIGN’s data and lignin suppliers) will be reported separately in sensitive (SEN) deliverables. More information regarding bioassays for application in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and fragrances of such depolymerized mixtures have been reported in deliverable D4.1 “Preliminary summary report bioassays of depolymerized lignin mixtures” submitted in project month 16. In parallel to this report, D4.4 “Preliminary report on depolymerized lignin mixture for cosmetic sector” will also be submitted. Finally, D4.2 “Preliminary report on depolymerized lignin mixture for pharma sector” and D4.6 “Preliminary report on depolymerized lignin mixture for fragrances sector will be available from project month 18.

3 Approach on the isolation and purification of bioactive compounds

3.1 Methodology for the isolation and purification of bioactive compounds

This work describes a multi-step purification strategy for isolating bioactive compounds from complex depolymerized lignin mixtures. During WP3, lignin is subjected to chemical and enzymatic depolymerization by KELADA and University of Helsinki (UH), aiming to produce fragments displaying bioactivity. This process yields a library of diverse molecules that need to be separated to isolate specifically those with potential applications in areas such as cancer treatment, cosmetics, or fragrances. To achieve this, the methodology employed consisted of a series of chromatographic methods. These methods allow, in a first step, the separation of the newly formed molecules into less complex fractions, from which the bioactive compounds can then be readily isolated using further chromatographic techniques. The workflow integrates solvent screening, high-pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC), flash column chromatography, and preparative high-performance liquid chromatography (prep. HPLC) to progressively reduce sample complexity and isolate the bioactive compounds of interest. Finally, for structural characterization of the isolated bioactive compound, mass-spectroscopy (MS) and nuclear magnetic resonance resonance (NMR) spectroscopy

Figure 1: Methodology used for the isolation and characterization of bioactive compounds formed during chemical or enzymatic depolymerization.

3.2 Step 1: HPLC and GPC

Depolymerized lignin mixtures obtained from various experimental conditions is first subjected to a solubility screening in a range of polar organic solvents to identify suitable media for downstream analysis. The depolymerized lignin mixtures showed good solubility in polar solvents such as acetonitrile (ACN), methanol (MeOH) and dimethylformamide (DMF), which were thus selected as primary solvents for HPLC (ACN or MeOH with water) and GPC (DMF). Solubilized depolymerized mixtures were then analysed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and size exclusion chromatography (SEC/GPC). These analyses served multiple purposes:

- Evaluation of the chemical complexity of the mixtures
- Evaluation of the fragment's size formed during depolymerization
- Preliminary identification of major and minor components
- Optimization of elution conditions (solvent composition, flow rate, gradient profiles) for use in preparative chromatography during step 2

The solvent system of water/acetonitrile or water/methanol was selected for reverse-phase separation due to its compatibility with both lignin-derived compounds and chromatographic equipment.

3.3 Step 2: Fractionation of depolymerized mixtures using flash column chromatography

During depolymerization of the lignin, a large number of different molecules or lignin fragments can be formed but not all will have the desired bioactivity. Because of this large variety of molecules present in the mixture, fractionation of the depolymerized mixtures using flash column chromatography allows us to sort such molecules based on polarity and produce less complex mixtures. Such fractions are later tested again by bioassays in order to identify the fractions that contain the targeted bioactive molecules. For this purpose, fractionation was carried out using an automated flash chromatography system from Büchi commercialized as **Sepacore** equipped with reverse-phase C18 columns and UV detectors. This setup mimics an HPLC setup. The fractions produced are further tested by our partners with a new series of bioassays. For pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications, the bioassays will be performed by "Fundación Medina" in Spain and for fragrances, this will be performed by the NOVA University of Lisbon.

3.4 Step 3: Isolation of bioactive compounds by means of preparative HPLC

Fractions that demonstrated significant bioactivity were further processed using preparative-scale HPLC, which offers higher resolution and compound purity. The preparative HPLC system operated under optimized gradient conditions derived from Step 1 allows higher separation power compared to flash chromatography in step 2 while still enabling sample volumes of up to 70 mg in 1.5 mL per run.

3.5 Step 4: Structural characterization

Lignin and its derivatives are known for being complex mixtures of molecules. Mass spectroscopy is a tool that allows the identification of a huge number of molecules in a mixture. Developing a reliable method is key. However, not all the molecules or mixtures behave in the same manner. Therefore, in UCD, we are trying various different conditions to establish a reliable method. In particular, samples are prepared and subjected to LC-MS ESI spectroscopy. The LC part of the instrument is equipped with a C-18 RF column (Poroshell 120 C18). Water with 0.1% TFA and methanol are used as eluent. The analysis is carried out in either positive or negative mode. The latter seems to provide better results. Commercially available compounds with structure and chemical similarity to lignin have been used and good analysis results have been achieved. Once a reliable method is fully developed, single components of bioactive interest will be analysable to assess which molecules are present.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Step 1: HPLC and GPC

The goal in step 1 was to gather information that would be useful during fractionation in step 2, which is finally the most critical step as the Sepacore does not possess the resolution than HPLC has in terms of separation and UV detection. For this reason, the depolymerized mixtures were first measured by means of HPLC and GPC under standard parameter settings. As an example, we can see the GPC and HPLC chromatograms of two different depolymerized mixtures that were used to develop method parameters in Figure 2. Both mixtures were produced from the same raw lignin (L01_05) that was extracted by enzymatic depolymerization and fractionation process. At this point, this lignin was the best candidate for chemical depolymerization as it contains a significant amount of β -O-4 and other internal linkage susceptible to break. From the GPC chromatographs (**Fig. 2A and B**), we can clearly observe that the depolymerized mixtures produced from the same lignin have different compositions in terms of size. Specifically, when method A was used to depolymerize lignin L01_05, a narrower distribution was obtained compared to method B. On the other hand, method B

seems to produce smaller fragments, as peaks with molecular weights (Mw) of 438 and 162 g/mol were detected, while the smallest fragments produced with method A are around 800 g/mol. Interestingly, when measured by HPLC, it's evident that method A produces a more complex mixture (**Figure 2C**), as the chromatogram shows higher amounts of peaks corresponding to individual fragments, compared to the chromatogram obtained using method B (**Figure 2D**).

Figure 2: GPC chromatogram of **(A)** depolymerized mixture A and **(B)** depolymerized mixture B compared to the raw lignin (L01_05). HPLC chromatogram of **(C)** depolymerized mixture A and **(D)** depolymerized mixture B.

4.2 Step 2: Flash column chromatography

Flash column chromatography was employed to purify a series of depolymerized lignin mixtures. This technique allowed for the separation of the complex mixtures, typically yielding between 3 and 5 distinct fractions per purified sample. Various eluents and gradient methods were evaluated and optimized to achieve the best possible separation of the target compounds.

For example, the depolymerized L01_05 (meth. B) mixture displayed in **Figure 2B** was successfully separated into 4 different fractions as displayed in **Figure 3A**. In there we can see 2 distinct peaks (F1 and F2), that probably corresponds to multiple compounds per peak, eluting within the first minutes (5 to 10 min) and a broader peak in the middle of the chromatograph that was split into two different fractions.

For this purification, the recollection of the fractions was performed collecting a defined amount of mL per fraction. In addition, the recollection could also be performed based on the absorbance of the UV detector. This would allow to collect fractions only when a fixed absorbance threshold is reached, resulting in fractions with higher purity but in exchange of mass recovery. Indeed, if a relatively high threshold is set to favour purity, whatever elutes below this threshold is discarded into the waste. At this point of the project the first approach was preferred because it allows to recover all the material in the different fraction and decreases the risk of losing bioactive compounds.

Such fractions were then measured by GPC (**Figure 3B**), and we could observe that F1 and F2 contained all the small molecules while F3 and F4 including molecules with higher molar masses. This last two fractions most probably contain either unreacted lignin fragments or

lignin that was depolymerized to only a low extent. This was further supported by FTIR measurement as the spectra of F3 and F4 matches almost perfectly the FTIR spectra of the starting lignin.

Figure 3: (A) Flash column chromatogram of depolymerized L01_05 (Meth B) recorded with a Sepacore system using multiple wavelength UV detectors. (B) Superposition of the GPC chromatographs of each fraction produced from depolymerized L01_05 (Meth B) by flash column chromatography.

The fraction produced were also measured by HPLC and we can observe that fractionations worked particularly well for a still not fully optimized method. This affirmation is based on the fact that each fraction, even if they may share some compounds, contains a significantly different composition that contains the essential of the peaks observed in the depolymerized mixture (**Figure 4**).

Additionally, the method could easily be adapted to this depolymerized mixture to improve the separation at the beginning of the chromatography. On the other hand, F3 and F4, specially F3, also contain molecules that elutes in the first minutes which should not be the case, but this could still be improved by tuning the gradient applied.

Nevertheless, the complexity of the mixture decreased to a level where the isolation of compounds of interest by prep. HPLC becomes easier and realistic. Using preparative HPLC to purify bioactive fractions, rather than the crude depolymerization mixture, allows to increase the amount of molecules of interest per injection. This approach avoids the inclusion of non-bioactive residues, decreasing the number of runs required to reach 10 mg of each possible bioactive compound (i.e. minimum amount required to perform complete bioassays).

Figure 3: Stacking of the HPLC-UV chromatograms of depolymerized LO1_05 lignin using method B and the 4 different fractions (F1 – F4) obtained after fractionation by flash column chromatography.

4.3 Step 3: Preparative HPLC

At this stage of the project, the initial fractions produced have been sent for bioassays to identify which fractions exhibit bioactivity in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances. The results are still pending. Ideally, the bioactivity observed in the first series of bioassays will be found in some individual fractions per depolymerized mixture. If this is the case, flash column chromatography will be repeated, focusing exclusively on the fractions of interest. These selected fractions will then be purified using preparative HPLC, where method development is currently on-going. With this new setup, we expect to be able to inject and purify from 7 to 70 mg of depolymerized mixture per run.

4.4 Step 4: Structural characterization

To assess whether the conditions implemented are the right ones to detect lignin and its derivatives, a similar model compound (GVG) was used. In the figure below, the top panel represent the number of charges detected, the central panel is chromatograms at 254 nm and the panel on the bottom is the mass detected by the instrument in negative mode. For this compound, the base peak is the one at 379.5 corresponding to its formate adduct.

Many samples made from Kelada have been analysed. Unfortunately, not many molecules were detected. Below there is an example (PLGN_VK_24_S2) showing a peak at 227.0. The isotopic distribution and the similarity with the lignin network lead us to infer that the peak at 227.0 corresponds to the poly-charged molecule shown in the picture.

We are currently looking for conditions that improve lignin fragment ionization. Use of buffers, different gradient or sample concentration, ionization voltage and injection temperature are some of the parameters we are tuning to improve these encouraging results. As an alternative or in addition, MALDI can be carried out for the identification of fashionable bioactive molecules.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

In conclusion, the PROSPLIGN project has successfully established a multi-step methodology for processing complex depolymerized lignin mixtures. Initial solvent screening followed by GPC and analytical HPLC (Step 1) provided crucial insights into the solubility characteristics and chemical complexity of the depolymerized lignin mixtures, informing the subsequent optimization of chromatographic conditions. Building upon this understanding, automated flash column chromatography (Step 2) methods were developed that proved to be reproducible for the fractionation of these complex mixtures, yielding consistent elution profiles and distinct fractions with reduced chemical complexity.

Looking ahead within PROSPLIGN, the generated fractions will now proceed to a comprehensive series of bioassays to identify those exhibiting target biological activities. Subsequently, the bioactive fractions will be further subjected to high-resolution preparative HPLC (Step 3). This crucial purification step will enable the isolation of individual molecules or mixtures of molecules responsible for the observed bioactivity, facilitating their subsequent structural characterization and evaluation for potential applications aligned with the PROSPLIGN project's objectives. An update on Task 4.4 will be provided in the next associated deliverable (D4.9 Preliminary report on isolation and purification of bioactive compounds), which is due for submission in M20.